

Understanding the contents of a lesson plan and the stages of a lesson

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Annotation. Aims are what teachers (and learners) want to achieve in a lesson or a course. Activity in a class is planned in order to achieve these aims.

A lesson aim could be for the learners to demonstrate that they understand the form or use of the passive better, or to have practised intensive reading. A course aim could be to improve the report writing skills of a group of business students.

Key words: content, to demonstrate, to improve, to create, to enable, to communicate, to involve, to identify.

Аннотация. Цели — это то, чего учителя (и учащиеся) хотят достичь на уроке или курсе. Деятельность в классе планируется для достижения этих целей.

Цель урока может состоять в том, чтобы учащиеся продемонстрировали, что они лучше понимают форму или использование пассивного залога, или попрактиковались в интенсивном чтении. Целью курса может быть улучшение навыков написания отчетов у группы студентов, изучающих бизнес.

Ключевые слова: контент, демонстрировать, улучшать, создавать, давать возможность, общаться, вовлекать, идентифицировать.

Introduction. The main tasks arising from the resolutions and decrees and speeches of President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev are to raise the level of education and upbringing of higher education workers, to ensure the full development of the nation's spirituality and knowledge, the humanities of public education, the involvement of advanced pedagogical technologies. [Mirziyoyev Sh.M. 2016]

We know that English is one of the second most spoken languages in the world. The number of learners of this language is growing day by day. In almost every corner of the world, there are many who speak and understand English. English is also the number one digital language of communication. Therefore, it is very important to teach English to the younger generation in order for our country to be among other countries in this period of rapid development. [Kuchkarova 2022]

There are numerous approaches of using targeted tactics to motivate language learners. We can review a few of the activities. In the classroom Aims on lesson plans often describe what the teacher wants learners to be able to do by the end of a lesson, or what they will have done during it. Teachers can tell learners their lesson aims, or involve learners in setting them. This can help create a sense of purpose and progress.

Main objective. A lesson plan's objective is to provide us with a framework for teaching. Because students will soon become bored if we only perform one thing (30 minutes of dictation is not very inspirational), our class will need to include a range of components, and the plan will help us organize these components. This arrangement should be logical and allow us to identify a connection between each of the components, leading us to the lesson plan's goal. In our planning, we must consider four factors, which are given in the boxes below:

2. Lesson Aim
What do we want to achieve in
this lesson?

1. The Class How many students,
ages, sexes, group dynamics etc.

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3. How to achieve the lesson aim
Which combination of activities
will be successful?

4. The unexpected What will we
do if something goes wrong?

We can plan the various stages of the lesson. There is no hard and fast rule, but you might want to try the following which many teachers find effective. We have broken the stages of a lesson into 5 components:

Stage 1 – Engagement activity

Stage 2 - Presentation

Stage 3 - Study

Stage 4 - Practice

Stage 5 – Warm down

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For this criteria match the examples below with the correct item.

- To enable the learner to communicate effectively and appropriately in real life situation.

- After a lesson on bullying, students will be able to explain the difference between a bully and a friend by writing a short paragraph that includes a thesis statement and call to action.

- Students will be able to categorize types of animals into the correct classes with a graphic organizer after reading an article on animal traits.

- To revise and reinforce structure already learnt

- To understand the total content and underlying meaning in the context.

- Students will be able to diagram the life cycle of a butterfly in a graphic organizer after reading *From Caterpillar to Butterfly*.

Compare lesson types and approaches to lesson planning. Grammar-based

Traditional language classes relied mainly on grammar-based teaching, with a lot of rule explanations, structure training, and translation tasks. However, totally reliant on grammar will not get you very far. It is more beneficial to have a large vocabulary. If you don't know the words 'want' and 'water,' knowing that in English pronouns must usually be expressed, that uncountable nouns don't take an article, or that the object follows the verb won't help you if you're dying of thirst in a scorching hot English-speaking country (although, let's face it, that's unlikely to be the case in the UK).

If you have extremely particular goals in mind when learning English, a private session may be the best option. The teacher may personalize the lesson to your individual needs. The intense one-to-one practise not only maximises your time with the teacher but also allows the teacher to focus on your specific areas of trouble and provide loads of feedback.

However, both sides in this style of lecture may be tempted to turn the class into a one-way interaction, with the teacher asking a lot of questions and the student only responding. In the case of English, in particular, this can be quite harmful to the student; question forms are tricky to master in English, and it's important that a student has lots of opportunity to practice them.

The mixed-ability group class is for students who have a variety of skills. This sort of class is frequently quite active, with the teacher maximizing student speaking

time through pair and group work activities and providing a healthy balance of receptive and productive skills practice (listening and reading) (speaking and writing). As part of a communication-based approach to learning, grammar is presented, practiced, and reviewed.

Conclusion. Every lesson needs a plan. The level of detail it contains, and whether it is mainly in your head or mainly on paper, will vary depending on your training and experience, the type of class (one-to-one classes often have a much more fluid plan, for example) and the time that you have available to plan.

The main reason to have a plan is to know, firstly, the aim of your lesson and, secondly, what you're going to do during the lesson in order to achieve that aim. If you don't know what you want your students to be able to do by the end of the lesson, you risk them going away feeling that they haven't achieved anything.

Questions to ask before making a lesson plan

1. Will you review what the school is teaching the students? Or will you create new learning goals? If the target language will be new, be sure it is appropriate for the students' level.

2. Will you focus on speaking, reading, writing or reading? Or a combination? Your school may have a preference.

3. Will you teach alone or will you have help? The simplest games, for example, can be difficult to teach without translation unless you are very prepared.

PPP will be an ESL teaching style that the ESL instructor will use frequently. In general, it is a fairly simple planning strategy that may be used effectively by even untrained teachers. It also fits well with methodologies like PBL for clarifying a linguistic point. PPP can be integrated into other models to some extent by more experienced teachers.

PPP is separated into three stages, each of which progresses from highly controlled to more free practice at the end. The presentation phase is teacher-centred, and teachers frequently employ multimedia to describe a situation. PPP is undoubtedly one of the most popular ESL teaching methods and approaches.

In most cases, the practice stage includes a tightly controlled practice phase in which participants rehearse the correct linguistic structure. Drills, multiple-choice tasks, and gap-filling are common in this stage. These activities help students to put what the teacher says in the presenting stage into practice. During this period, there

will be a lot of teacher feedback and a lot of error correction. In order to properly prepare for the final phase, the teacher will also model correct forms.

The production stage is the final level of PPP.

This level allows participants to put what they've learned in the previous two stages into practice. Participants create oral or written writings during this stage. Dialogues, oral presentations, and the creation of various sorts of writing are common activities here. During the production stages, there will be minimal to no teacher involvement.

Task-based language teaching is another name for TBL (task-based learning) (TBLT). During the execution of significant tasks, participants use English. Participants will use authentic language that is contextualized to the activity in order to complete meaningful activities.

The work will not consist of a structure, a vocabulary point, or anything similar. If that's the goal, PPP, not TBL, is the way to go. TBL, on the other hand, focuses on meaning in context. For example, in an English for Emails course, the assignment would be to write an email inquiring about product availability. It might also be making a group film in a session with a different focus.

There are 3 phases in a TBL lesson, Pre-task, Task and Post-task.

1. The teacher contextualizes the lesson and piques the students' interest in the task during the pre-task.

2. Communication will be emphasized at the Task stage. At this point, the teacher will not do much in the way of error correction. The emphasis is on students using the target language rather than on correcting them. It's critical that the participants complete the assignment without being interrupted. The teacher would keep an eye on the students and collaborate with them, but not interrupt them.

3. The post-task will be a participant evaluation of the task. During this stage, it is common to observe presentations and peer review discussions. Of course, the language that formed during the Task stage will be present in these activities.

Test, Teach, Test is a teaching approach in which students accomplish an initial assignment or activity without the assistance of the teacher. Quite sometimes, it will be an exam or a quiz. After that, the teacher will examine the test results and begin teaching the target language. Finally, the instructor allows the students to practice the target language. TTT is a short teaching method that can be used as a tool to monitor learning throughout other teaching tactics.

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